

"Ship in bottle" Porph@MOMs as highly efficient catalysts for selective controllable oxidation and insights into different mechanism in heterogeneous and homogeneous environment

M. Saghian^a, [S Dehghanpour](#),^{a,*} and M. Sharbatdaran^b

^a Department of Chemistry, Alzahra university, P.O. Box 1993891176, Tehran, Iran. E-mail: Dehghanpours@alzahra.ac.ir; Fax: +982188041344

^b Physics and accelerators School, Nuclear Sciences and Technology Research Institute, Karaj, Iran

Abstract

In the present work, three "ship in bottle" Porph@MOMs are reported as biomimetic oxidation catalysts for different reactions. The frameworks are constructed from trimesic acid and metal ions (M= Fe, Co and Mn) in which tetra(*N*-methyl-4-pyridyl) porphyrin (MTMPyP) is encapsulated within the cavities. Additionally, the catalytic activity of the corresponding homogeneous compounds, FeTMPyP, CoTMPyP and MnTMPyP, and the frameworks without porphyrins within the cavities were investigated in the foregoing oxidation reactions. The prepared 3D porous structures have the ability to control selectivity toward the desired product. Furthermore, they are capable of acting as effective peroxidase mimics, which successfully catalyze oxidation of diverse olefins as well as hydrocarbons using TBHP as oxidant. The heterogeneous catalysts significantly enhance conversion in contrast to their corresponding homogeneous systems. Remarkably, an insight into the catalyst behavior was gained from the proposed mechanism based on the reversal of selectivity. Investigation of the stability and reusability of the catalysts revealed the heterogeneity character of the catalyst with no desorption during the course of oxidation reactions. High yields, clean reactions, high thermal stability and reusability of catalysts, make them good candidates for heterogeneous catalyst in various oxidation reactions.

Link: <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlelanding/2018/nj/c8nj00315g/unauth#!divAbstract>